

Capturing and Preserving Indigenous Knowledge (IK) For Posterity: A Case of Okpe Culture in Delta State

Onome N. Ekoko

Delta State University, Abraka,
onomealakpodia@gmail.com, onekoko@delsu.edu.ng
ORCID: 0000-0003-3228-3677

Ese Emenal

Delta State University, Abraka,
emenalgoldenese@gmail.com

Violet E. Ikolo

Delta State University Library, Abraka,
v.ikolo@gmail.com, v.ikolo@delsu.edu.ng
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8103-6827>
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Abstract

Purpose: The study examined Okpe elders' perceptions of the capture and preservation of aspects of their culture and indigenous knowledge.

Methodology: Adopting a survey design, the study relied on the perceptions of elderly individuals in the Okpe kingdom to elicit their responses regarding the capture and preservation of certain aspects of the culture. The study used a purposive sample of 25 elderly people from the Okpe kingdom located across the state. A questionnaire was used to collect data from participants, and researchers personally interacted with them to ensure that the questions were understood.

Findings: The study found that elders wanted aspects such as language, music, and festivals to be captured and preserved for posterity. Just over half (52%) agreed that traditional medicine should also be captured; however, the elders in Okpe did not want the aspect of female circumcision to be preserved.

Conclusion: The elders of the Okpe kingdom believe in capturing and preserving some aspects of their IK for future generations.

Study Implications: The study suggests that librarians, as professionals, are working to preserve knowledge and develop methods to capture the abundance of IK, ensuring that future generations have access to their roots and heritage.

Study type: Research Paper

Keywords: Indigenous Knowledge, Okpe, Culture, preservation, Delta State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Indigenous knowledge (IK) comprises knowledge, cultural practices, and ideas that aim to maintain, convey, and sustain indigenous links with cultures over time (Bruchac, 2014). IK is knowledge primarily produced by indigenous peoples and, in most cases, takes on different meanings across cultural contexts. It is information transmitted verbally through practice and observation in a dynamic manner tailored to the demands of a particular community. IK is diverse, complex, and often neglected in modern and recorded knowledge because of the common notion that it is primitive, backward, sometimes savage, rural, unverified, and unscientific (Ezeanya-Esiobu, 2019). IK has been applied to many areas. According to Agada et al. (2022), IK is used to sustain the community and its culture. Utilising indigenous knowledge and placing value on it could advance societal and socioeconomic goals while also enhancing cultural identity, as in public health and sustainable agriculture. There is a strong,

favourable debate among numerous authors (Odora-Hoppers, 2002; Dei, 2000; da Silva et al., 2023) about the need to capture, record, and hand down vast amounts of IK useful to societal development. Ensuring that indigenous knowledge does not become extinct is the goal of many cultural heritage institutions, which systematically endeavour to preserve individuals' heritage. Sadly, many indigenous customs are disappearing because their progenitors are dying out without, as it were, passing the torch. Sometimes, the people to whom it is passed on show little regard for these legacies or fail to follow the guidance they receive. Furthermore, there aren't enough measures in place to prevent indigenous knowledge bearers from abusing their expertise. Records of historical customs are currently being retained, and indigenous knowledge preservation is receiving greater attention than it has in the past so that the younger generation can benefit and know their heritage (Oyelude, 2023).

Ensuring the accessibility of IK is the responsibility of knowledge workers, such as librarians, who capture and preserve this information to help other researchers and indigenous populations find and retrieve pertinent information (Balogun, 2023). However, the majority of IK is in the form of tacit knowledge, making it difficult to explain and transfer to younger generations, especially as those who hold it are becoming fewer each day. In addition, there is the question of which aspects of IK require capturing and preserving. Consequently, it is expedient to undertake a study that investigates the perceptions of older people about the aspects of IK that need to be preserved and retained, using the indigenous people of Okpe in Delta State, Nigeria, as a case study.

Research Questions

1. How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the Okpe language?
2. How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the Okpe Music?
3. How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the Okpe cultural festivals?
4. How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the traditional medicine practice of the Okpe people?
5. How do elders perceive the retention of circumcision practices of the Okpe people?

Literature Review

The Concept of Indigenous Knowledge (IK)

Indigenous Knowledge (IK) is defined as the unique, traditional, local knowledge existing within and developed around the specific indigenous cultures of people in a particular geographic area (Sen, 2005, as cited by Slade & Yoong, 2014). Zidny and Eilks (2020) define IK as the local knowledge held by local peoples, unique to their culture or society. It is also understood as a unique, local, contextual knowledge, abilities, and skills that originate with the people native to a particular place, accumulated through many years of experience, learning, development, and verbal transmission. To Emeagwali (2014), it is the cumulative strategies, techniques, practices, intellectual resources, tools, explanations, cultural beliefs, and values of a group of people, accumulated over time in a particular locality with less interference and imposition from external forces. According to Mokhles (2019), IK is also referred to as local knowledge, folk knowledge, or traditional science. It is the unique knowledge confined to a particular culture or society. One unique feature of IK is that it is produced and passed on from one generation to another to help people adapt to their own socio-economic environments. In all, IK provides rich contexts that may help clarify how environmental, social, and spiritual conceptions of nature and life relate to one another (Zidny & Eilks, 2020).

From a cultural perspective, Jacob et al. (2015) explained that IK is an integrated system of information comprising human knowledge, beliefs, and behaviour. It encompasses experiential knowledge and addresses the diverse and complex aspects of the lives of the local inhabitants. For instance, livelihoods, spirituality, ontological realities, land, sociocultural music, word games, speech, writing, language,

scientific discoveries, life skills, and other education-centred activities are all driven by IK of the people in the locality. It is usually the obligation of one generation to pass down the knowledge to another generation in different ways. According to Oyelude (2023), a common practice in many modern civilisations is to record and preserve the oral indigenous traditions for future generations, or ensure they do not disappear with the passing away of the community's elders.

Features of IK:

IK has some distinct features that set it apart from other types of knowledge. Zidny and Eilks (2020) enumerated some of these features to include:

- IK is locally rooted: Usually originating from a particular community and situated within broader cultural traditions; it is a set of experiences generated by people living in those communities. Therefore, IK can get dislocated if relocated to different locations.
- IK is mostly tacit in nature: it involves knowledge that is not easily codifiable. It is information derived from an individual's feelings, experiences, insights, observations, and perceptions, and is not easy to explain or convey to others.
- Transmitted orally: IK is mostly transmitted by demonstration and emulation. Some of its qualities might be lost in the process of codification.
- Experiential instead of theoretical knowledge: IK is continuously reinforced by experience, attempts and testing in the demanding laboratory of local communities' existence.
- Learned via recurrence, which characterises tradition even in the face of the addition of new information. Repetition helps people remember and reinforce IK.

Indigenous traditions have various facets that warrant extraction and preservation. One of these is the local and traditional medicines of indigenous people. According to Anyaoku et al. (2015), the gradual extinction of IK systems in African communities is evident, particularly in the context of IK in traditional medicine. The adoption of Western cultural practices has caused serious harm to our indigenous culture, resulting in the systematic loss of vital knowledge about a people. The authors further argued that the conservation of traditional medical knowledge aims to safeguard it and prevent its extinction. This is because such knowledge, therapies, and practices ought to be valued, maintained, encouraged, and correctly disseminated. The planned documentation of the current body of knowledge can achieve this. Similarly, Zimu-Biyela (2016) noted that the sharing of knowledge through communal meetings, which has long been practised by communities, is rapidly disappearing because knowledge is not being captured and preserved. Coleman (2013) provides evidence that those with knowledge of traditional medicine preserve it through apprenticeship, which occurs under the guidance of a recognised practitioner who imparts it to the trainee over many years and is paid for training others. The implication here is that individuals who are experts are the only ones who can share this knowledge with others, and this cannot be regarded as a reliable way to preserve this knowledge because of what will happen to this knowledge when the expert vanishes or dies.

The Okpe People

Many authors have argued that the Okpe are a distinct ethnic group from the Urhobo. The Okpe kingdom was founded in the seventeenth century. They are said to have migrated to present-day Sapele. The capital of the Okpe kingdom is Orokerpe. It occupies a large expanse of land, approximately 500 sq. km., comprising the mainland, mangroves, swamps, and rivers (Erivwo 1991). Okpe has over 23 communities, with rivers and vast forest areas. This ethnic nationality inhabits the hinterland of the Niger Delta, between longitude 50 301 and 600 251 East, and latitude 60 and 50 151 North, in what is known as Delta State of Nigeria. To the north are Benin, to the south the Ijaw, to the east the Ukwuani (in Aboh Division), and to the west the Itsekeri (Erivwo 1991). It is politically divided into the Okpe

and Sapele Local Government Areas of the state. Okpe is bounded to the southwest by Agbarho, Warri, and Uvwie (Effurun) within its boundaries. It borders Oghara, Jesse, Benin, and Agbon to the northeast (Idamoyibo, 2006). The Orodje of Okpe is the title of the traditional king of Okpe. The four governing dynasties alternate in holding the throne, and Major General Felix Mujakperuo is the current Orodje and the monarch of the Okpe Kingdom (Guardian Nigeria News, 2017). The Okpe speak a common language known as Okpe. Speech intonation distinguishes homonyms from tonality.

Methodology

This study is a survey based on the perceptions of elderly individuals. The study drew on a population of elderly people from the Okpe kingdom, located across the state. Twenty-five elderly indigenes were purposively selected to meet the criterion of being aged 65-90. This was done to capture only those perceived to have in-depth knowledge of Okpe customs, traditions, and culture. They were selected from the marketplace, social functions, and a church. A simple, self-designed questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Section A and Section B. The first section collected basic demographic information, while the second part asked about elders' perceptions of various aspects of the culture they sought to preserve. The questionnaire was read aloud to participants who could not read, and their responses were recorded accordingly; others completed their own forms. This was deemed necessary to capture the respondents' thoughts in detail, as their opinions and perspectives were obtained in their real-life contexts. The data collected were analysed using simple percentages and presented in pie charts.

Table 1: Respondents' Biodata

Respondents	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	11	44
Female	14	56
Age		
70-80	13	52
81-90	8	32
Above 90	4	16

Demographic information for the participants in Table 1 indicates that 14 (56%) were female and 11 (44%) were male. Their age distribution showed that participants aged 71-80 (52%) were the largest group, whereas those aged 90 and above (16%) were the smallest.

Research Question 1: How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the Okpe language?

Figure 1 presents the elderly's perceptions of the retention of the Okpe language and its transmission to the next generation. All 24 (100%) participants agreed that the language should be preserved for the next generation.

Research Question 2: How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the Okpe Music?

Figure 2 shows the elders' perception of the retention of Okpe music and its transmission to the next generation. Most (18, 62%) of the participants agreed that Okpe music must be captured and transmitted to future generations to enjoy and improve upon. However, 11 (38%) did not see the need to capture and transmit Okpe music.

Research Question 3: How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the Okpe cultural festivals?

Figure 3 shows how the elders perceive the preservation and transmission of Okpe festivals. 15 (62%) elders believe that the Okpe festivals are important and should be captured and preserved for future generations.

Research Question 4: How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the traditional medicine practice of the Okpe people?

Figure 4 shows that 13 (52%) of the elders agreed that the Okpe people's traditional medical knowledge should be recorded and preserved for future generations, while 12 (48%) did not support the preservation and transmission of this knowledge.

Research Question 5: How do elders perceive the capturing and preservation of the circumcision practices of the Okpe people?

Figure 5 presents the perceptions of Okpe elders regarding the preservation of the circumcision rites for young females to be married in the Okpe kingdom. The majority (15; 60%) did not want this cultural practice transmitted to future generations, whereas 10 (40%) wanted it transmitted.

Discussion

Throughout this study, it was evident that participants sought to preserve certain aspects of their indigenous culture and knowledge for future generations. As a perception study, the aim was to capture the views of older members of the Okpe kingdom on the preservation of their unique culture, even among the Urhobo-speaking people of Delta State. One of the most distinctive aspects of Okpe culture is its language. It identifies and differentiates its people from other ethnic Urhobo-speaking cultures in the state. According to Idamoyibo (2006), the Okpe language is tonal, with homonyms distinguished by speech intonation. It is therefore not surprising that 100% of the study's participants agreed to the preservation of their language. This finding corroborates the result reported by Nwagbo (2022), who investigated the use of the minority language Okpe in Lagos and found that attitudes toward Okpe among the older generation and a minority of the younger generation were positive. The preservation of the language was most common among older Okpe people, who spoke it primarily to their spouses, whereas they spoke it to their children less frequently, using English and Nigerian Pidgin. Additionally, the older generation of Okpe used the language minimally with Okpe-speaking friends and kinfolk, and in expressing their traditions. A significant majority of the young generation was not proficient in the language. Idamoyibo (2006) also noted that, although there have been attempts to develop a more scientific orthography, more than 90% of the literate Okpe populace are unable to read, understand, or speak the language.

The perspectives of elders were also sought regarding the documentation and retention of Okpe music. The Okpe musical culture is highly important to them because it affects many aspects of their daily lives. Their music, like their language, is widely regarded as unique and distinct from the traditional music of other Urhobo-speaking populations in Delta State. Numerous songs are sung at religious ceremonies, celebrations, and funerals. Perhaps for this reason, the elders agreed that Okpe music must be preserved and transmitted to future generations for their enjoyment and improvement. This finding confirms that of Edah and Idolor (2023) on the musical practice associated with puberty rites in the Okpe Kingdom, which is currently dwindling, as noted in the 2008 World Health Organisation declaration on the practice of circumcision. Similarly, Igbi and Ogbeide (2019) stressed that, through music, Nigerian traditional cultures share some characteristics; more intriguingly, each ethnic group or culture has its own musical style that makes it identifiable, and research efforts must be intensified to

sustain these traditions over time. Idolor (2020) also rightly expressed his fear that, if attempts are made to repackage elements of culture, such as music, the alarm facing endangered languages will not only cease to exist, but the much-needed sustenance will also be lost.

Another very interesting aspect of Okpe culture is its festivals. The primary purpose of a festival in Africa is to celebrate and foster joy. Okpe elders agreed to the documentation and preservation of the cultural festivals. According to Adjeketa et al. (2024), festivals in the Okpe Kingdom are occasions for giving gratitude to God, the Almighty, and for appeasing the gods of the forest and water, as well as the ancestors or ancestral spirit. The events also provide residents with the opportunity to see their families at least once a year when they travel home. Unresolved conflicts and miscommunications are resolved during these sessions. As a result, this fosters harmony and tranquillity both within the family unit and across the community. The event contributes to the dissemination, preservation, and global projection of Okpe culture. On this occasion, tourists are taught local dances, music, drumming, and artwork.

Those who favoured the capture and preservation of the Okpe people's traditional medicines constituted slightly more than half of the total respondents. This implies that while some wanted the traditional medicine practice to continue, others didn't. The reason those who do not want the traditional medicine captured and preserved may lie in the explanation offered by Ottuh and Ottuh (2020), who note that although Urhobo traditional medicine is effective, it is widely perceived as associated with fetishism. It is also stressed that traditional medicine is grounded in crudeness. The authors further pointed out that if this attitude continued in Urhobo land, there is a tendency that Urhobo traditional medical care will go unnoticed. Also, Akpomovie (2017) argues rather vigorously that both the indigenous healthcare delivery system in Urhobo land and Western orthodox medical practices should be integrated in Nigeria, as is the case in other parts of the world.

Okpe elders did not support the idea of capturing and preserving the circumcision rites for young females who are to be married in the Okpe kingdom. The research did not explore their reasons for opposing the documentation and preservation of this aspect of the Okpe people's cultural practices. However, their reasons may not be far-fetched, given that circumcision is today seen as a barbaric act and has been banned in many countries of the world. This finding does not align with the previous finding reported by Umukoro and Onoyona (2016), which stated that although the culture of female circumcision has generated criticism and is opposed by many who have tagged it barbaric and inhuman around the world, it is still being practised among the Udu-speaking people of Urhobo in Delta State of Nigeria. In a similar study carried out by Akindola and Abiola (2019) to investigate the link between poverty, culture, and female circumcision/female genital mutilation in three local government areas of Nigeria's Ekiti State, the study found that FC/FGM is mostly caused by a cultural concept that has been practised in certain cultures for millennia rather than poverty. The authors concluded from their findings that these communities are not likely to heed the ongoing global advice to discontinue the practice, hence their insensitivity to the much-publicised associated risks.

Conclusion

The elders of the Okpe kingdom in Delta State firmly believe in the importance of capturing and preserving IK for future generations. They see it as a vital effort to ensure that the rich and essential aspects of their culture—such as language, music, and festivals—are not lost over time. While there are divided opinions on traditional medicine, it is evident that the elders are embracing modernisation and agree that practices like female circumcision should be left behind. Their proactive approach underscores a deep commitment to safeguarding their cultural heritage for posterity.

Librarians have always been advocates for knowledge transfer and preservation from generation to generation. There is an abundance of IK not just among the Okpe people but also among several other

cultural groups in Nigeria. If this knowledge is not captured and preserved, it will be lost, and with it, several important aspects of the culture. It is important that librarians and related professionals develop strategies to capture and preserve our cultural heritage so that future generations have access to it.

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